

Scenario

Informed consent, privacy and data protection in relation to multimodal video data: an educational scenario

Researcher A was part of a team working on an NWO funded project into the use of dance as a methodology for supporting people's affective understanding of the enduring legacy of Dutch slavery and colonisation. Following completion of the project researcher A began studying for a PhD and contacted the PI to request use of the data to extend the research in order to gain further insight into how participants made sense of the dance experiences, emotionally and conceptually. The proposal was accepted and the researcher was given guest status at the original institution to allow continued access to the data. It was later decided, in collaboration with the data management officers at both the original and researcher's new host institution, that a Joint Controllers Data Exchange Agreement be set up to put the project on a more formal footing and to allow transfer of data to the local servers for processing purposes.

The data-set consists primarily of videoed multimodal interviews, supported by videos of participation in dance/movement workshops and group discussions, written comments and demographic information including the special category of (self-defined) cultural heritage. Pseudonymised codes are used for the subjects but their faces, voices and clothing are evident in the videos. The data will be viewed by Researcher A, their two supervisors (at two different institutions – the new base and another), and potentially, both select colleagues for guidance, and student assistants for ELAN coding. Faces can be blurred in the videos without compromising the usefulness of the data.

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Questions

The information sheet given to participants for the grounding of consent, stated that "The research data we collect during this study will be used by researchers as part of data sets, articles and presentations." Beyond that, "anonymized research data is [also] accessible to other scientists for a period of at least 10 years" and that "when we share data with other researchers, these data cannot be traced back to you." Specifically, the information states that "Some portions of the multimodal (i.e., audio and visual) information will also be annotated and analysed". The consent forms covers "permission for us to make and use these recordings for a) research purposes and b) academic communication and publication (in which case, faces will be blurred for anonymity)."

1. Is this extension project effectively covered by the participants' informed consent?
2. Given that video data cannot be fully anonymized, who can legitimately be given permission to view the files?
3. Should the new parties engaged in the follow-up project, including the supervisors, be considered 'researchers' or 'other scientists', as per the information sheet phrasing? In either case, should steps be taken to mask identities, such as blurring faces, before the videos are viewed by anyone who was not part of the original research team?